

GS/S/E/Fq2 (1)
(cE8)

SHERD SHEET

MATCH WITH OTHER CORPORA

CORPUS	WARE DESIGNATION	TYPE DESIGNATION
	"MUD" WARE	

I. TECHNIQUE

A. HAND MADE	1. Hand Modelled	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	2. Coiling	<input type="checkbox"/>	3. Plate Building	<input type="checkbox"/>
	4. Core Moulding	<input type="checkbox"/>	5. Turntable (up. pt.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	6. Other	<input type="checkbox"/>
B. TURNTABLE			C. WHEELMADE			E. CASTING

II. FABRIC

A. TEXTURE OF CLAY

GENERAL:	Coarse <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Medium	Fine
1. Pebble	<input type="checkbox"/>	2. Granule	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Medium	<input type="checkbox"/>	6. Fine	<input type="checkbox"/>
		3. Very Coarse	<input type="checkbox"/>
		7. Very Fine	<input type="checkbox"/>
		4. Coarse	<input type="checkbox"/>
		8. Silt	<input type="checkbox"/>

B. COMPOSITION Type of Clay: *Nic Alluvial*

TEMPER (General):	Heavy <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Medium	Light
1. Material	<i>Chaff</i>	<i>Pottery Flecks</i>	<i>Few Mica flecks</i>
2. Particle Size	<i>med.</i>	<i>Sand</i>	

C. FRACTURE COLOR

General Description	CEC	Munsell
<i>Pink Brown</i>		<i>H12</i>

D. HARDNESS *SOFT*

E. POROSITY

F. TRANSVERSE STRENGTH

G. PERMEABILITY

III. SURFACE PROPERTIES

A. SURFACE TREATMENT

1. Untreated	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	2. Wheel Finish	<input type="checkbox"/>	a. ribbing	<input type="checkbox"/>	b. scrapped or shaved	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Hand Finish	a. smoothed	<input type="checkbox"/>	b. polished by burnishing	<input type="checkbox"/>	c. polished by rubbing	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	d. scrapped	<input type="checkbox"/>	e. scratched or combed	<input type="checkbox"/>	f. other	<input type="checkbox"/>	
4. Coating	a. wash	<input type="checkbox"/>	b. slip	<input type="checkbox"/>	c. glaze	<input type="checkbox"/>	

B. SURFACE TEXTURE *SOFT ROUGH*

C. MECHANICAL CONDITION OF SURFACE

D. LUSTER 1. Matte 2. Low 3. Medium 4. High

E. SURFACE COLOR

General Description	Munsell CEC
<i>Grey Brown</i>	<i>C9</i>

IV. DECORATION

A. TECHNIQUE

1. Incised	<input type="checkbox"/>	2. Impressed	<input type="checkbox"/>	3. Gouged	<input type="checkbox"/>	4. Pinched	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Modelled	<input type="checkbox"/>	6. Moulded	<input type="checkbox"/>	7. Painted	<input type="checkbox"/>	8. Inlaid	<input type="checkbox"/>